

Potentiometric Studies on the Formation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Lanthanides with Eriochrome Blue Black-R in Presence of Aminopolycarboxylic Acids

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Spectrophotometric and potentiometric study on binary complexes of 3-hydroxy-4-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylazo)-1-naphthalene sulphonic acid (Eriochrome Blue Black-R) (EBBR) (Fig. 1) with some lanthanide metal ions have been reported by different authors^{1,2}. In our earlier studies, we reported formation of binary and ternary complexes of Eriochrome black-T³ and Calmagite⁴ in presence of aminopolycarboxylic acids potentiometrically. The present communication reports the potentiometric study involving the formation of ternary complexes of EBBR with lanthanides (trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Gd, Dy and Y) in presence of aminopolycarboxylic acids, hydroxyethyliminodiacetic acid [HIMDA], nitrilo-triacetic acid (NTA), hydroxyethylenethylenediamine triacetic acid (HEDTA) and ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA). The studies have been carried out in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol media at 30° and $I = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄). The proton-ligand stability constants and the binary metal-ligand stability constants have been obtained by Irving and Rossotti titration technique⁵. The ternary metal-ligand formation constants have been obtained

by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santhappa⁶. The distribution of various species as a function of pH has been calculated by using the computer program BEST⁷.

Results and Discussion

In the ternary systems studied, the mixed ligand curves closely follow the 1 : 1 Ln(III)-A (where A = HIMDA and NTA) binary curves in the lower pH (< 4.0) region, until the protons of aminopolycarboxylic acids were neutralised, indicating that the binary Ln(III)-A complexes predominate in this region. In the higher pH region the divergence of the ternary curve from those of the binary Ln(III)-A system reveals the formation of ternary complexes of the type [Ln-A-EBBR]. Here, EBBR acts as secondary ligand. The formation of ternary complexes were supported by non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve in the region of mixed ligand complex formation. It is observed that in the lower pH range the major species were the free metal ion and the Ln-A species, whereas in the higher pH range the major species were Ln-A and Ln-A-EBBR.

Fig. 1. Structure of EBBR.

However, in the case of HEDTA and EDTA, the experimental titration curves as well as theoretical composite curves do not indicate the formation of [Ln-A-EBBR] ternary complexes. The absence of ternary complexes were further supported by

blue colour due to free EBBR^{2-} ion at pH 6 during the titration.

The relative order of stability constants (Table 1) in all the metal ligand systems in terms of metal ions was found to be $\text{La}^{\text{III}} < \text{Pr}^{\text{III}} < \text{Nd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Gd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Dy}^{\text{III}} > \text{Y}^{\text{III}}$, which might be attributed to the decreasing size and increasing charge/radius ratio of the metal ion. The order of stabilities with respect to primary ligands was $\text{HIMDA} > \text{NTA}$. This was due to the charge neutralisation as well as denticity of the ligands⁸.

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY METAL COMPLEXES OF SOME LANTHANIDES WITH ERIOCHROME BLUE BLACK-R (L) IN 50% (v/v)

Medium : 50% (v/v) aq. methanol, Temp. = 30°, $I = 0.1 \text{ M} (\text{NaClO}_4)$

Constant	La^{III}	Pr^{III}	Nd^{III}	Gd^{III}	Dy^{III}	Y^{III}
$\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$	9.80	10.87	11.11	11.91	12.14	11.99
$\log K_{\text{ML}_2}^{\text{M}}$	7.90	9.27	9.57	10.26	10.48	10.26
$\log K_{\text{M(HIMDA)}}^{\text{M}}$	8.57	8.67	9.78	9.01	9.08	9.06
$\log K_{\text{M(NTA)}}^{\text{M}}$	10.06	10.28	10.49	10.72	10.88	10.78
$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$						
A = HIMDA	8.20	9.32	9.65	10.34	10.54	10.40
A = NTA	7.61	8.66	8.81	9.69	10.00	9.63
$\Delta \log K$						
A = HIMDA	-1.6	-1.55	-1.46	-1.57	-1.60	-1.59
A = NTA	-2.19	-2.21	-2.30	-2.22	-2.14	-2.16

Limit of error, ± 0.05 log units.

Ligand $\log K_{1\text{H}}$ and $\log K_{2\text{H}}$: 11.70 and 6.90; HIMDA 8.67 and 2.30; NTA 10.00 and 3.70.

The negative $\Delta \log K$ values⁸ (Table 1) revealed that the formation of ternary complexes was not favoured over that of the binary ones. This may be due to the availability of lesser number of coordinating sites for EBBR on primary complex $[\text{Ln-A}]$ than on the free $\text{Ln}(\text{Aq})^{3+}$ ions⁹. The non-formation of ternary complexes in presence of HEDTA and EDTA may be due to the hexa-dentate nature of HEDTA and EDTA.

Experimental

The metal solutions were prepared by dissolving lanthanide nitrates in double-distilled water and were standardised complexometrically¹⁰. EBBR was

purified by reported method¹¹ and was prepared in pure methanol. Sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised by the usual methods. HIMDA (Fluka), NTA (Sigma), HEDTA (Fluka) and EDTA (B.D.H.) solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

An Elico LI-120 pH meter with a combined electrode was used for the measurement of hydrogen ion concentrations. A thermostat with regulating accuracy of $\pm 0.05^\circ$ was used.

The procedure for pH-metric titrations was the same as described earlier^{3,4}. In case of binary system the metal-ligand ratio was kept at 1:5 and for ternary system a molar ratio 1:1:1 was maintained. The ionic strength ($I = 0.1 \text{ M}$) was maintained by adding neutral sodium perchlorate. All the sets of solutions were titrated against standard alkali. pH meter reading in 50% (v/v) methanol-water was corrected by the method of Van Uitert and Haas¹².

References

1. S. M. F. RAHMAN, N. AHMAD and J. AHMED, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 531.
2. J. R. NARKHEDE and G. S. NATARAJAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 131.
3. B. STAYANARAYANA, K. L. OMPRAKASH, A. V. C. PAL and M. L. N. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 710.
4. B. SATYANARAYANA, K. L. OMPRAKASH, M. L. N. REDDY and A. V. C. PAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 172.
5. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
6. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTHAPPA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1623; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 38.
7. R. J. MOTEKAITIS and A. E. MARTELL, *Can J. Chem.*, 1982, **60**, 2403.
8. H. SIGEL, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1975, **14**, 394.
9. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORAAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 89.
10. G. SCHWARZENBACH, "Complexometric Titrations", Methuen, London, 1956.
11. G. L. SILVER and R. C. BOWMAN, *Talanta*, 1967, **14**, 983.
12. L. G. VAN UITERT and G. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.